

Supplementary Data

Novel variants and phenotypes in *NEUROG3* associated syndrome

Karn Wejaphikul^{1,2,#}, Khomsak Srilanchakon^{3,#}, Wuttichart Kamolvisit^{4,5}, Supavadee Jantasuwan^{4,5}, Kanokwan Santawong^{4,5}, Siraprapa Tongkobpetch^{4,5}, Thanakorn Theerapanon⁶, Alisara Damrongmanee¹, Nattaphorn Hongkawong¹, Nuthapong Ukarapol¹, Prapai Dejkhamron^{1,2}, Vichit Supornsilchai³, Thantrira Porntaveetus^{6,*}, Vorasuk Shotelersuk^{4,5}

¹Department of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

² Northern Diabetes Center, Faculty of Medicine, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai, Thailand

³Division of Endocrinology, Department of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok 10330, Thailand

⁴Center of Excellence for Medical Genomics, Medical Genomics Cluster, Department of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

⁵Excellence Center for Genomics and Precision Medicine, King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital, the Thai Red Cross Society, Bangkok, 10330, Thailand

⁶Center of Excellence in Genomics and Precision Dentistry, Department of Physiology, Faculty of Dentistry, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok 10330, Thailand

#Equal contribution

NEUROG3 protein 10 ug

Supplementary Figure 1. Immunoblots showed the expression of the wild type, the p.Arg95Pro, and the p.Thr124Arg at similar size (30 kDa) and GAPDH as loading control (37 kDa).

Supplementary Table 1. List of genes related to malabsorption examined in this study according to HP: 0002024 in Human Phenotype Ontology.

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>ABCB11</i>	OMIM:601847,OMIM:605479,ORPHA:69665
<i>ABCB4</i>	OMIM:602347,ORPHA:69663,OMIM:614972,ORPHA:69665,OMIM:600803
<i>ACOX2</i>	OMIM:617308
<i>ADAMTS3</i>	ORPHA:2136,OMIM:618154
<i>AGA</i>	OMIM:208400,ORPHA:93
<i>AIRE</i>	ORPHA:3453,OMIM:240300
<i>AK2</i>	ORPHA:33355,OMIM:267500
<i>AKR1D1</i>	OMIM:235555,ORPHA:79303
<i>AMACR</i>	OMIM:614307,ORPHA:79095,OMIM:214950
<i>ANTXR2</i>	ORPHA:2028,ORPHA:2176,OMIM:228600
<i>APC</i>	ORPHA:261584,OMIM:114500,OMIM:114550,ORPHA:3258,OMIM:175100,ORPHA:79665,ORPHA:99818,ORPHA:247806,OMIM:135290,ORPHA:873,OMIM:613659,OMIM:619182
<i>ARX</i>	OMIM:300215,OMIM:300419,ORPHA:777,ORPHA:452,OMIM:309510,ORPHA:2508,OMIM:308350,ORPHA:3451,OMIM:300004,ORPHA:1934,ORPHA:94083,ORPHA:3175
<i>ASXL1</i>	ORPHA:97297,ORPHA:98850,ORPHA:98849,OMIM:614286,OMIM:605039
<i>ATP7A</i>	OMIM:309400,ORPHA:388,ORPHA:565,ORPHA:198,OMIM:304150,OMIM:300489
<i>ATP8B1</i>	OMIM:211600,OMIM:243300,OMIM:147480,ORPHA:69665
<i>BLNK</i>	OMIM:613502,ORPHA:33110
<i>BMPRIA</i>	ORPHA:440437,ORPHA:329971,OMIM:174900,ORPHA:79076,ORPHA:157794,OMIM:610069
<i>BTK</i>	OMIM:300755,OMIM:307200,ORPHA:47
<i>C4A</i>	ORPHA:117,OMIM:614380
<i>CALR</i>	ORPHA:824,OMIM:187950,ORPHA:3318,ORPHA:131,OMIM:254450
<i>CAVI</i>	OMIM:606721,ORPHA:528,ORPHA:220402,OMIM:612526,OMIM:615343,ORPHA:220393
<i>CBL</i>	ORPHA:648,ORPHA:98850,OMIM:607785,OMIM:613563
<i>CBLIF</i>	OMIM:261000
<i>CCBE1</i>	ORPHA:2136,OMIM:235510
<i>CCDC47</i>	OMIM:618268
<i>CD55</i>	OMIM:226300,OMIM:613793
<i>CD79A</i>	ORPHA:33110,OMIM:613501
<i>CD79B</i>	OMIM:612692,ORPHA:33110
<i>CDCA7</i>	OMIM:616910,ORPHA:2268
<i>CFTR</i>	ORPHA:48,OMIM:219700,ORPHA:399805,ORPHA:676,OMIM:277180,ORPHA:498359,OMIM:167800,ORPHA:60033,OMIM:211400,ORPHA:586
<i>CIITA</i>	OMIM:209920,ORPHA:572,OMIM:180300
<i>CISD2</i>	OMIM:604928,ORPHA:3463
<i>CLMP</i>	ORPHA:2301,OMIM:615237

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>COX4I2</i>	OMIM:612714
<i>CTC1</i>	OMIM:612199,ORPHA:1775
<i>CTNNB1</i>	OMIM:155255,ORPHA:891,OMIM:114500,OMIM:114550,OMIM:167000,OMIM:132600,ORPHA:33402,ORPHA:54595,ORPHA:873,OMIM:615075,OMIM:617572,ORPHA:404473
<i>CTRC</i>	ORPHA:676,OMIM:167800,ORPHA:103918
<i>CYBA</i>	ORPHA:379,OMIM:233690
<i>CYBB</i>	ORPHA:379,OMIM:306400,OMIM:300645
<i>CYBC1</i>	ORPHA:379,OMIM:618935
<i>CYP7B1</i>	ORPHA:79302,ORPHA:100986,OMIM:270800,OMIM:613812
<i>DKC1</i>	ORPHA:3322,ORPHA:1775,OMIM:305000
<i>DMP1</i>	OMIM:241520,ORPHA:289176
<i>DNAJC21</i>	OMIM:617052,ORPHA:811,OMIM:260400
<i>DNAJC30</i>	ORPHA:104,OMIM:619382,ORPHA:904
<i>DNMT3B</i>	OMIM:242860,OMIM:619478,ORPHA:2268,ORPHA:269
<i>DZIP1L</i>	OMIM:617610,ORPHA:731
<i>EDNRA</i>	OMIM:157300,OMIM:616367,ORPHA:586
<i>EFL1</i>	OMIM:617941,ORPHA:811
<i>ELN</i>	ORPHA:91387,OMIM:185500,ORPHA:90348,OMIM:123700,OMIM:194050,ORPHA:3193,ORPHA:904
<i>ENPP1</i>	OMIM:615522,ORPHA:758,OMIM:613312,ORPHA:51608,OMIM:601665,OMIM:125853,OMIM:208000,ORPHA:289176
<i>EPCAM</i>	OMIM:613244,ORPHA:144,OMIM:613217,ORPHA:92050
<i>ERCC2</i>	ORPHA:910,OMIM:278730,ORPHA:220295,OMIM:601675,ORPHA:33364,ORPHA:1466,OMIM:610756
<i>F5</i>	OMIM:227400,OMIM:614389,OMIM:188055,OMIM:600880,OMIM:601367,ORPHA:131,ORPHA:326
<i>FAN1</i>	ORPHA:144,OMIM:614817
<i>FAS</i>	ORPHA:3437,ORPHA:117,OMIM:601859,ORPHA:3261
<i>FAT4</i>	OMIM:616006,ORPHA:2136,OMIM:615546,ORPHA:314679
<i>FCGR2A</i>	OMIM:219700,OMIM:152700
<i>FLNA</i>	ORPHA:1826,OMIM:300244,OMIM:311300,OMIM:300048,OMIM:309350,OMIM:300321,ORPHA:90652,OMIM:304120,ORPHA:2301,OMIM:305620,OMIM:314400,ORPHA:99811,ORPHA:90650,ORPHA:75497,ORPHA:98892,ORPHA:2484,OMIM:300049
<i>FOXP3</i>	ORPHA:37042,OMIM:304790
<i>GCLC</i>	OMIM:230450,ORPHA:33574,ORPHA:586
<i>GLA</i>	ORPHA:324,OMIM:301500
<i>HELLS</i>	OMIM:616911,ORPHA:2268
<i>HFE</i>	OMIM:176200,OMIM:104300,ORPHA:465508,OMIM:235200,ORPHA:586,OMIM:176100
<i>HLA-B</i>	ORPHA:36426,OMIM:106300,ORPHA:397,ORPHA:117,ORPHA:3287,ORPHA:29207

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>HLA-DQA1</i>	OMIM:212750,ORPHA:930
<i>HLA-DQB1</i>	OMIM:123400,OMIM:126200,ORPHA:83465,OMIM:212750,ORPHA:930,ORPHA:2073,ORPHA:703
<i>HLA-DRB1</i>	ORPHA:797,OMIM:126200,ORPHA:220402,ORPHA:83465,ORPHA:397,ORPHA:545,ORPHA:747,ORPHA:85414,OMIM:181000,ORPHA:2073,ORPHA:220393,ORPHA:703
<i>HMOX1</i>	OMIM:606963,OMIM:614034,ORPHA:586
<i>HPGD</i>	ORPHA:1525,OMIM:119900,OMIM:259100,ORPHA:217059,ORPHA:2796
<i>HSD3B7</i>	ORPHA:79301,OMIM:607765
<i>HYOU1</i>	OMIM:233600
<i>IFNGR1</i>	OMIM:600263,OMIM:615978,ORPHA:117,OMIM:209950
<i>IGHM</i>	OMIM:601495,ORPHA:33110
<i>IGLL1</i>	OMIM:613500,ORPHA:33110
<i>IL10</i>	ORPHA:117,OMIM:180300
<i>IL23R</i>	ORPHA:117
<i>IRF4</i>	ORPHA:3452
<i>IRF5</i>	ORPHA:220402,ORPHA:186,ORPHA:220393
<i>JAK2</i>	OMIM:133100,OMIM:614521,OMIM:601626,ORPHA:824,OMIM:600880,OMIM:263300,ORPHA:71493,ORPHA:3318,ORPHA:131,OMIM:254450,ORPHA:729
<i>KCNN4</i>	ORPHA:3202,OMIM:616689,ORPHA:586
<i>KDM6A</i>	OMIM:147920,OMIM:300867,ORPHA:2322
<i>KMT2D</i>	OMIM:147920,ORPHA:2322
<i>KRAS</i>	OMIM:609942,OMIM:601626,ORPHA:144,OMIM:108010,ORPHA:2612,OMIM:615278,ORPHA:2396,OMIM:614470,ORPHA:1333,OMIM:613659,OMIM:600268,OMIM:260350,ORPHA:1340,ORPHA:3339,ORPHA:648,OMIM:211980,OMIM:109800,OMIM:114480,OMIM:163200
<i>LBR</i>	OMIM:613471,OMIM:169400,ORPHA:779,OMIM:215140,ORPHA:1426
<i>LCT</i>	OMIM:223000
<i>LIG4</i>	OMIM:606593,OMIM:254500,ORPHA:39041,ORPHA:99812,ORPHA:235
<i>LIPA</i>	ORPHA:75233,OMIM:278000,ORPHA:75234
<i>LPIN2</i>	OMIM:609628,ORPHA:77297
<i>LRRC8A</i>	OMIM:613506,ORPHA:33110
<i>MADD</i>	ORPHA:528084,OMIM:619005,OMIM:619004
<i>MCM6</i>	OMIM:223100
<i>MEFV</i>	ORPHA:3243,OMIM:134610,OMIM:249100,OMIM:608068,ORPHA:342,ORPHA:117,ORPHA:329967
<i>MIF</i>	ORPHA:85414,ORPHA:586
<i>MLH1</i>	OMIM:276300,OMIM:609310,OMIM:158320,ORPHA:587,ORPHA:144
<i>MLH3</i>	OMIM:114500,ORPHA:144,OMIM:608089,OMIM:614385
<i>MLXIPL</i>	OMIM:194050,ORPHA:904
<i>MSH2</i>	OMIM:619096,OMIM:158320,ORPHA:587,ORPHA:144,OMIM:120435

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>MSH6</i>	ORPHA:587,ORPHA:144,OMIM:619097,OMIM:608089,OMIM:614350
<i>MTOR</i>	OMIM:616638,ORPHA:457485,OMIM:607341
<i>MTTP</i>	OMIM:605552,OMIM:200100,ORPHA:14
<i>MYD88</i>	ORPHA:33226,OMIM:153600,ORPHA:183713,OMIM:612260
<i>NCF1</i>	ORPHA:379,OMIM:233700,ORPHA:904
<i>NCF2</i>	OMIM:233710,ORPHA:379
<i>NCF4</i>	ORPHA:379,OMIM:613960
<i>NEUROG3</i>	ORPHA:83620,OMIM:610370
<i>NHP2</i>	OMIM:224230,ORPHA:1775,OMIM:613987
<i>NOPI0</i>	OMIM:224230,ORPHA:1775
<i>NPM1</i>	OMIM:601626,ORPHA:520,ORPHA:1775
<i>NSUN2</i>	ORPHA:88616,OMIM:611091,ORPHA:235
<i>OCRL</i>	ORPHA:534,OMIM:300555,OMIM:309000
<i>PARN</i>	ORPHA:3322,OMIM:616371,ORPHA:2032,ORPHA:1775,OMIM:616353
<i>PCSK1</i>	OMIM:600955,ORPHA:71528
<i>PEX1</i>	OMIM:214100,OMIM:234580,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,OMIM:601539,ORPHA:912,ORPHA:3220
<i>PEX10</i>	OMIM:614870,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:247815,ORPHA:912,OMIM:614871
<i>PEX11B</i>	OMIM:614920,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912
<i>PEX12</i>	ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,OMIM:266510,ORPHA:912,OMIM:614859
<i>PEX13</i>	ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,OMIM:614883,ORPHA:912,OMIM:614885
<i>PEX14</i>	OMIM:614887,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912
<i>PEX16</i>	ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,OMIM:614876,OMIM:614877,ORPHA:912
<i>PEX19</i>	ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912,OMIM:614886
<i>PEX2</i>	OMIM:614867,OMIM:614866,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912
<i>PEX26</i>	OMIM:614872,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912,OMIM:614873
<i>PEX3</i>	OMIM:614882,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912,OMIM:617370
<i>PEX5</i>	OMIM:202370,ORPHA:44,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912,OMIM:616716,OMIM:214110
<i>PEX6</i>	OMIM:614863,ORPHA:95433,ORPHA:44,OMIM:614862,OMIM:616617,ORPHA:772,ORPHA:912,ORPHA:3220
<i>PGM3</i>	ORPHA:443811,OMIM:615816
<i>PIK3CA</i>	OMIM:167000,OMIM:162900,ORPHA:144,OMIM:612918,ORPHA:60040,ORPHA:2495,OMIM:613659,OMIM:114500,OMIM:114550,OMIM:602501,OMIM:613089,ORPHA:201,OMIM:211980,OMIM:114480,OMIM:182000,OMIM:615108,ORPHA:276280,OMIM:155500,ORPHA:99802
<i>PIK3R1</i>	OMIM:269880,ORPHA:33110,OMIM:615214,ORPHA:3163,OMIM:616005
<i>PKHD1</i>	OMIM:263200,ORPHA:731,ORPHA:53035
<i>PMS1</i>	ORPHA:144,OMIM:120435
<i>PMS2</i>	OMIM:614337,ORPHA:144,OMIM:619101

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>PNLIP</i>	OMIM:614338
<i>POLG</i>	ORPHA:298,ORPHA:70595,OMIM:258450,ORPHA:254892,OMIM:203700,OMIM:603041,ORPHA:726,ORPHA:254886,OMIM:157640,OMIM:613662,OMIM:607459,ORPHA:94125
<i>PRSS1</i>	ORPHA:676,OMIM:167800
<i>PRSS2</i>	ORPHA:676,OMIM:167800
<i>PTF1A</i>	OMIM:615935,OMIM:609069,ORPHA:65288
<i>PTRH2</i>	OMIM:616263,ORPHA:456312
<i>RECQL4</i>	ORPHA:1225,OMIM:266280,OMIM:268400,ORPHA:221016,OMIM:218600
<i>RFX5</i>	OMIM:209920,ORPHA:572
<i>RFX6</i>	OMIM:615710
<i>RFXANK</i>	OMIM:209920,ORPHA:572
<i>RFXAP</i>	OMIM:209920,ORPHA:572
<i>RMRP</i>	OMIM:607095,ORPHA:175,OMIM:250250,OMIM:250460,ORPHA:39041
<i>RTEL1</i>	ORPHA:3322,OMIM:616373,OMIM:615190,ORPHA:2032,ORPHA:1775
<i>RUNX1</i>	OMIM:601626,ORPHA:98850,OMIM:601399,ORPHA:521
<i>SAR1B</i>	ORPHA:71,OMIM:246700
<i>SATB1</i>	OMIM:619228,ORPHA:528084,OMIM:619229
<i>SBDS</i>	OMIM:609135,ORPHA:811,OMIM:260400,ORPHA:88
<i>SEMA4A</i>	ORPHA:440437,ORPHA:1872,ORPHA:791,OMIM:610282,OMIM:610283
<i>SERPINA1</i>	ORPHA:60,OMIM:613490,ORPHA:586
<i>SH3KBP1</i>	OMIM:300310
<i>SHPK</i>	OMIM:617213,ORPHA:440713
<i>SI</i>	ORPHA:35122,OMIM:222900
<i>SLC10A2</i>	OMIM:613291
<i>SLC11A1</i>	ORPHA:3389,ORPHA:586
<i>SLC29A3</i>	ORPHA:168569,ORPHA:1782,OMIM:602782
<i>SLC2A2</i>	OMIM:125853,OMIM:227810,ORPHA:2088
<i>SLC39A4</i>	OMIM:201100,ORPHA:37
<i>SLC46A1</i>	ORPHA:90045,OMIM:229050
<i>SLC51B</i>	OMIM:619481
<i>SLC5A1</i>	ORPHA:35710,OMIM:606824
<i>SLC6A19</i>	ORPHA:42062,OMIM:234500,OMIM:242600,ORPHA:2116,OMIM:138500
<i>SLC7A7</i>	OMIM:222700,ORPHA:470
<i>SLC9A3</i>	OMIM:616868,ORPHA:586
<i>SLCO2A1</i>	OMIM:167100,OMIM:614441,ORPHA:2796
<i>SPINK1</i>	ORPHA:676,OMIM:608189,OMIM:167800,ORPHA:103918
<i>SPINK5</i>	OMIM:256500,ORPHA:634
<i>SRP54</i>	ORPHA:486,OMIM:618752,ORPHA:811,OMIM:260400

Genes	Disease_IDs
<i>STAT4</i>	ORPHA:85408,ORPHA:93552,ORPHA:85410,ORPHA:117
<i>TCF3</i>	OMIM:616941,ORPHA:33110
<i>TERC</i>	OMIM:127550,ORPHA:2032,ORPHA:88,OMIM:614743,ORPHA:1775
<i>TERT</i>	ORPHA:3322,OMIM:601626,OMIM:615134,ORPHA:2495,ORPHA:88,OMIM:178500,OMIM:609135,OMIM:127550,ORPHA:618,OMIM:614742,ORPHA:2032,OMIM:613989,ORPHA:1775
<i>TET2</i>	OMIM:619126,ORPHA:75564,ORPHA:98850,ORPHA:824,ORPHA:98849,ORPHA:98826,ORPHA:3318,OMIM:614286,ORPHA:729
<i>TGFB1</i>	OMIM:219700,ORPHA:1328,OMIM:618213,OMIM:131300,ORPHA:586
<i>TGFBR2</i>	ORPHA:91387,ORPHA:99977,ORPHA:144,OMIM:614331,OMIM:133239,OMIM:610168,ORPHA:60030
<i>TINF2</i>	ORPHA:3322,OMIM:268130,OMIM:613990,OMIM:127550,ORPHA:1775
<i>TJP2</i>	OMIM:615878,OMIM:607748
<i>TREH</i>	OMIM:612119,ORPHA:103909
<i>TRMT5</i>	OMIM:616539
<i>TRNK</i>	OMIM:540000,ORPHA:1349,OMIM:545000,ORPHA:551,ORPHA:255210,ORPHA:225
<i>TRNL1</i>	ORPHA:550,ORPHA:663,OMIM:540000,OMIM:545000,ORPHA:551,ORPHA:255210,ORPHA:480,ORPHA:225
<i>TYMP</i>	ORPHA:298,OMIM:603041
<i>UBR1</i>	ORPHA:2315,OMIM:243800
<i>USB1</i>	OMIM:604173,ORPHA:1775
<i>WFS1</i>	ORPHA:411590,OMIM:222300,OMIM:125853,OMIM:116400,OMIM:600965,OMIM:614296,ORPHA:3463
<i>WRAP53</i>	ORPHA:1775,OMIM:613988
<i>XRCC4</i>	OMIM:616541,ORPHA:99812,ORPHA:436182
<i>ZBTB24</i>	ORPHA:2268,OMIM:614069

Supplementary Table 2. Plasmid transfection.

Condition	Plasmid	Volume (ng/μl)
Empty	pCMV6-XL5 backbone	300
	pGL4-NEUROD1	100
	pGL4 vectors	100
Wild type	pCMV6-XL5-NEUROG3_WT	300
	pGL4-NEUROD1	100
	pGL4 vectors	100
R95P	pCMV6-XL5-NEUROG3_R95P	300
	pGL4-NEUROD1	100
	pGL4 vectors	100
T124P	pCMV6-XL5- NEUROG3_T124P	300
	pGL4-NEUROD1	100
	pGL4 vectors	100
Control	GFP	500

Supplementary Table 3. Summary of clinical phenotypes and *NEUROG3* variants reported in the literatures to date.

No.	Author	Sex	Onset of GI symptom	Details of GI symptoms	Histopathologic features	EECs	IDDM (onset)	Additional features	Age at the last exam	Variants
1	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2006)	M	1 m	Severe intractable malabsorptive diarrhea (ceased only with fasting), dehydration, severe hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	Normal intestinal mucosa	One EEC in > 350 small-bowel crypts and none in the colon	No	-	Died at 3 y	Homo. p.R107S
2	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2006)	M	4 d	Severe malabsorptive diarrhea (stopped promptly after fasting), dehydration, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	Normal intestinal mucosa	1 EEC in 100 crypts in the duodenum and 8 in 100 crypts in the jejunum	Yes (8 y)	FTT	8 y	Homo. p.R93L
3	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2006)	M	12 d	Severe malabsorptive diarrhea (markedly reduced stool volume after NPO), dehydration, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	Normal intestinal mucosa	1 EEC in 100 crypts in the duodenum and 8 in 100 crypts in the jejunum	Yes (8 y)	FTT, symptomatic hypocalcemia with vitamin D deficiency rickets	9 y	Homo. p.R93L
4	Rubio-Cabezas <i>et al.</i> (2011)	F	Since feeding started	Severe malabsorptive diarrhea since significant enteral feeding started which required mixed enteral and parenteral treatment	Normal intestinal mucosa	Complete absence of EECs in both colon and small bowel	Yes (1 d)	FTT	35 m	C.Het. p.E28* and p.L135P
5	Pinney <i>et al.</i> (2011)	F	Since birth	Persistent nonbloody malabsorptive diarrhea, abdominal distension, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	Moderate to severe villous blunting and atrophy with mild crypt hyperplasia	Complete absence of EECs in small intestine	Yes (5.5 m)	FTT, TPN induced cholestasis	Died at 10 m	Homo. p.E123*
6	Sayar <i>et al.</i> (2013)	F	20 d	Severe dehydration, metabolic acidosis, intractable malabsorptive diarrhea (cessation during fasting)	Normal villous structure and crypt-villus axis	No EEC in the duodenum and 3 per 50 crypts in the colon	No	-	20 m	Homo. p.S171fs

No.	Author	Sex	Onset of GI symptom	Details of GI symptoms	Histopathologic features	EECs	IDDM (onset)	Additional features	Age at the last exam	Variants
7	Ünlüsoy Aksu <i>et al.</i> (2016)	M	Since birth	Weight loss and high-volume watery diarrhea (volume decreased dramatically when enteral feeds were stopped), hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	Normal esophagus, gastric and duodenal mucosa	1 EEC per crypt in the duodenum	No	-	2 y 5 m	Homo. p.R93L ^b
8	Rubio-Cabezas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	F	N/A	Congenital diarrhea	N/A	N/A	Yes ^a (6 m)	SS (Ht -3 SDS), isolated HH, genu valgum, cubitus valgum, short neck	23 y	Homo. p.L135P
9	Rubio-Cabezas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	M	N/A	Congenital diarrhea	N/A	N/A	Yes (13 y)	SS (Ht -5.7 SDS), isolated HH, genu valgum	19 y	Homo. p.L135P
10	Rubio-Cabezas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	F	N/A	Congenital diarrhea	N/A	N/A	Yes (14 y)	SS (Ht -4.7 SDS), isolated HH	20 y	Homo. p.R107S
11	Rubio-Cabezas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	M	N/A	Congenital diarrhea	N/A	N/A	No	SS (Ht -4.6 SDS), isolated HH	24 y	Homo. p.R107S
12	Germán-Díaz <i>et al.</i> (2017)	M	11 d	Severe dehydration, metabolic acidosis, high-volume malabsorptive watery diarrhea	Normal duodenum and colonic mucosa (at the age of 4 m) Moderate villous atrophy with increased intraepithelial lymphocytes (at the age of 11 y)	3 EECs in 10 crypts in the duodenum and no ECs identified in colon	Yes (11 y)	FTT	16 y	Homo. p.R107S
13	Hancili <i>et al.</i> (2017)	M	15 d	Abdominal distension, persistent malabsorptive diarrhea, indirect hyperbilirubinemia (cholestasis and reduced intrahepatic biliary tracts)	Immature ganglion cells (known as neurointestinal dysplasia)	Complete absence of EECs in colon	Yes (2 m)	FTT (Ht -5.68 SDS and Wt -7.2 SDS), atypical triangular-shape face, low set ears, convergent strabismus, nails dysplasia, scrotal hypoplasia with glanular hypospadias (normal testosterone response by hCG stimulation), neuromotor and mental	4 y 9 m	Homo. p.Q4*

No.	Author	Sex	Onset of GI symptom	Details of GI symptoms	Histopathologic features	EECs	IDDM (onset)	Additional features	Age at the last exam	Variants
								retardation, dilated third and bilateral lateral ventricles, subclinical hypothyroidism with thyroid gland hypoplasia		
14	Hancili <i>et al.</i> (2017)	F	16 d	Congenital malabsorptive diarrhea, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis,	Unspecific signs of moderate inflammation,	Complete absence of EECs in colon	Yes (13 d)	FTT (Ht -4 SDS and Wt -1 SDS), hypertension,	6 y 10 m	Homo. p.Q4*
15	Solorzano-Vargas <i>et al.</i> (2020)	M	First week after birth	Severe diarrhea, weight loss, dehydration	N/A	Complete lack of EECs in intestine	Yes (3 y)	-	16 y	Homo. p.T40fs ^b
16	Solorzano-Vargas <i>et al.</i> (2020)	F	First week after birth	Severe diarrhea, weight loss, dehydration	N/A	Complete lack of EECs in intestine	Yes (7 y)	-	14 y	Homo. p.H144fs
17	Azab <i>et al.</i> (2020)	M	Since birth	Severe dehydration, nonbloody malabsorptive diarrhea, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis,	Normal esophagus, stomach, and duodenum, preserved villous architecture, well-developed brush border, no increased intraepithelial lymphocytes, no crypt hyperplasia	Less than 2 EECs per 10 crypts in the duodenum	No	FTT, TSH elevation (required LT4 treatment)	Died at 15 m	Homo. p.T138R
18	Current study (Pt-1)	F	21 d	Chronic diarrhea, wide anion gap metabolic acidosis	Normal esophagus, duodenal and ileum mucosa	Complete absence of EECs in small intestine	Yes (10 y)	GHD (Peak GH 1.5 ng/mL from clonidine test and Peak GH 4.6 from glucagon test [NR >7]), central hypothyroidism (FT4 0.6; reference 0.8 - 1.8 ng/dL, TSH 1.98; 0.35 - 4.94 mU/L) , pituitary gland hypoplasia, TPN induced cholestasis, camptodactyly, leg length discrepancy	14 y	Homo. p.T124R

No.	Author	Sex	Onset of GI symptom	Details of GI symptoms	Histopathologic features	EECs	IDDM (onset)	Additional features	Age at the last exam	Variants
19	Current study (Pt-2)	F	2 wk	Chronic malabsorptive diarrhea	Duodenal epithelial atrophy, crypt proliferation, villous shortening, eosinophilic infiltration	N/A	Yes (7 y)	GHD (GH 0.876 ng/mL during hypoglycemia [NR >7]), delayed puberty (no secondary sex characteristic at the age of 18 years), proximal renal tubulopathy (hypokalemia with normal AG metabolic acidosis [Na 135, K 2.9, Cl 122, CO ₂ 6 mmol/L, AG 7] and evidence of renal electrolyte loss [TTKG 5.1, urine pH 5.0, urine anion gap -18 mEq/L, U _{Ca} /U _{Cr} 1.16 mg/mg (NR <0.2), TRP 42.5%, and TMP/GFR 0.56 (NR <1.15-2.44)])	Died at 18 y	Homo. p.R95P
20	Current study (Pt-3)	M	1 m	Chronic malabsorptive diarrhea, hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis, bowel dilatation	Small nerve fibers with no ganglion cells at distal colon and rectum	N/A	Yes (7 y)	GHD (peak GH 5.09 ng/mL from clonidine test and 3.66 from L-Dopa test [NR >7]), HH (peak LH 1.2 IU/L after GnRHa stimulation at the age of 15 years [NR for puberty >5 IU/L]), central hypothyroidism (FT4 0.71; reference 0.98- 1.63 ng/dL, FT3 3.13; 2.56-5.01, TSH 0.38; 0.51-4.3 mU/L, pituitary gland hypoplasia, proximal renal tubulopathy (persistent hypokalemia, hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, and hypomagnesemia with evidence of renal electrolyte loss (U _{Ca} /U _{Cr} 0.34 mg/mg [NR<0.2], TRP 78%))	16 y	Homo. p.R95P

AG, anion gap; **C.Het.**, compound heterozygous; **EECs**, enteroendocrine cells; **F**, female; **FTT**, failure to thrive; **GH**, growth hormone; **GHD**, growth hormone deficiency; **GnRHa**, gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogue; **Homo.**, homozygous; **Ht**, height; **hCG**, human chorionic gonadotropin; **HH**, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism; **LT4**, levothyroxine; **M**, male; **m**, month; **N/A**, not available; **NR**, normal range; **SS**, short stature (with no evidence of GHD); **TMP/GFR**, the ratio of phosphorus tubule maximum to glomerular filtration

rate; **TRP**, tubular reabsorption of phosphate; **TSH**, thyroid stimulating hormone; **TTKG**, Trans Tubular Potassium Gradient; **U_{Ca}/U_{Cr}**, spot urine calcium to creatinine; **wk**, week; **Wt**, weight; **y**, year

^aThis patient had transient neonatal DM that relapsed at 6 years of age.

^bThe variants were corrected from the original publications according to HGVS nomenclature. The p.T40fs was reported in the original article as p.P39PfsX38 (Solorzano-Vargas *et al.*, 2020).

References for Supplementary Table 3.

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Supplementary Table 4. Clinical phenotypes of patients carrying *NEUROG3* variants reported in the literature to date.

Clinical features/Symptoms	Frequencies in previously reported 17 patients	Frequencies in 3 patients in this study	Overall frequencies
Male: Female	10:7	1:2	11:9
Neonatal onset of GI symptoms	13/13 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	16/16 (100%)
Malabsorptive diarrhea	11/17 (64.7%)	2/3 (66.7%)	13/20 (65%)
Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis	7/17 (41.2%)	1/3 (33.3%)	8/20 (40%)
Cholestasis	1/17 (5.9%)	0/3 (0%)	1/20 (5%)
Histologic findings of the intestine			
– Villous blunting and atrophy	2/11 (18.2%)	1/2 (50%)	3/13 (23.1%)
– Depleted or immature ganglion cells	1/11 (9.1%)	½ (50%)	2/13 (15.4%)
– Depleted or absent of EECs	13/13 (100%)	1/1 (100%)	14/14 (100%)
Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus	12/17 (70.6%)	3/3 (100%)	15/20 (75%)
Growth failure	12/17 (70.6%)	3/3 (100%)	15/20 (75%)
Pituitary hormone deficiencies	4/17 (23.5%)	3/3 (100%)	7/20 (35%)
Pituitary gland hypoplasia	0/17 (0%)	2/3 (66.7%)	2/20 (10%)
Proximal renal tubulopathy	0/17 (0%)	2/3 (66.7%)	2/20 (10%)